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Climate Change and Resource Conservation: Approaches to Sustainable Agriculture

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Editorial

The developing nations of the world continue to face the two most critical concerns i.e. rapidly growing population and corresponding food consumption. These challenges could be achieved by boosting agricultural productivity using mineral fertilizers and pesticides. However, such agricultural techniques inspired by the green revolution have led to the dramatic decrease in soil fertility and ecological resilience (Singh et al., 2019). So, it argues for sustainable agriculture techniques that combine traditional healthy practices with contemporary agricultural growth. As a result, sustainable farming techniques are expected to be resource-efficient and robust to the current scenario of climate change.

The climate change occurs naturally but humans have had a major impact on this process. Temperature, precipitation pattern and intensity, carbon dioxide levels and the amount of solar radiations are only few of the variables that negatively affect the agricultural productivity (El-Ramady et al., 2013). This necessitates the incorporation of climate-smart farming methods in order to guarantee a sufficient food supply for the estimated nine billion people in the world by the year 2050 (Taylor et al., 2018). For instance, a number of climate-smart agricultural management practices are being widely implemented to improve soil organic carbon sequestration, minimize greenhouse gas emissions while simultaneously ensuring crop productivity. Some of these practices include conservation tillage, biochar application, stress-tolerant seed varieties, cover crops, crop rotation and diversification, water and nutrient management. In addition, there has been an increase in the adoption of innovative sustainable agriculture practices to enhance crop production. For example, there is a huge surge of interest in the application of nanofertilizers for biofortification of plants to increase agricultural yields (Basavegowda and Baek, 2021). The novel nano-seed priming methods in seed technology are being explored to maintain the sustainability of seed quality and safety (Shelar et al., 2021).

Additionally, the need for sustainable and cleaner production is driving an increase in the hunt for agricultural approaches that save energy and resources. For this purpose, several practices have been suggested for the conservation of resources, restoration of soil health and sustenance of crop productivity. A comprehensive strategy is needed to solve the issues associated with energy-intensive production systems since many modules in various agro-ecosystems, such as energy efficiency, energy productivity and production economics are intricately linked. The conservation of resources, the development of adaptation strategies and considerable reduction in greenhouse gas emissions are all absolutely necessary for the achievement of sustainable goals in agriculture system. Therefore, this special issue will concentrate on the idea of sustainable agriculture, why it's important right now, and a critical look at the challenges and opportunities it presents for global sustainability.

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